

Psychology capital and organizational commitment of novice police: the mediation effect of career adaptability

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ABSTRACT

This research aims to provide an understanding of the mechanisms underlying organizational commitment (OC) by utilizing psychological capital (PsyCap) as an antecedent and career adaptability (CA) as a mediator in this relationship. This study employs the conservation of resources (COR) theory to elucidate how PsyCap and CA can assist organizational members in enhancing OC when assessing the workforce quality in police settings. The study was conducted at police academy and state police school in Indonesia. The sampling technique adopted purposive sampling, targeting novice police totaling 417 individuals. Concerning the relationship between PsyCap and CA denoting a statistically significant positive relationship. This indicates that as PsyCap increases, CA tends to rise as well. The results demonstrate that the relationship between PsyCap and OC is not statistically significant. The relationship between CA and OC indicates an extremely significant positive relationship, meaning that a higher CA leads to an elevated OC. The indirect relationship between PsyCap and OC, when considering the mediating effect of CA on the relationship between PsyCap and OC, implies that PsyCap has a significant positive influence on OC through CA. It can be concluded that CA fully mediates the relationship between PsyCap and OC.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Recent discussions surrounding psychological capital (PsyCap), career adaptability (CA), and organizational commitment (OC) have garnered significant attention, prompting researchers to delve deeper into these issues. The cultivation of PsyCap is perceived as a requisite condition for organizational members to augment their knowledge and skills, which subsequently influences the quality of work life and overall life quality [1]. Within any organizational context, the responsibilities and behaviors of its members can catalyze superior performance. Chen *et al.* [2] posited in their research that PsyCap is a precursor to the work attitudes of organizational members. Indeed, several literature sources have confirmed the relationship between PsyCap and job satisfaction, OC, and employee performance [3]–[5].

In non-profit-oriented organizations, job satisfaction and OC are arguably more inclined to exert a positive influence compared to organizations where members exhibit insufficient OC [6]. Furthermore, when organizational members possess a high level of PsyCap, it facilitates the organization in achieving its objectives, enhancing work accomplishments, and fortifying their intrinsic OC [7]. Given the critical role of OC for both the organization and the individual, it is imperative to investigate methods to bolster OC within the police workforce. However, existing studies have scarcely explored the influential constructs, such as the PsyCap of the police workforce, and other mediating constructs concerning the quality of OC within the police academy and state police school in Indonesia. Consequently, this study aims to probe the mechanism of PsyCap in enhancing OC via CA within the police workforce.

Research concerning the relationship between PsyCap, CA, and OC has been discovered in various organizations. For instance, studies related to OC have shown an increase within the police staff over recent years [8]. Gasic and Pagon [9] posited in their study that OC in police departments can be maximized by ensuring accurate job and work environment expectations held by new members; and by ensuring that police officers feel valued and supported by the organization through programs that enhance decision-making, elevate job-related skills, and offer satisfying career options. In the healthcare sector, OC is perceived as an essential component required to work in healthcare organizations due to the significance of employee commitment, especially when the internal environment tends to be less supportive [10].

A research [11] defined OC in as the strength of an individual's identification and involvement in a specific organization. Indeed, OC can be distinguished by three characteristic factors: a strong belief and acceptance of organizational goals; a willingness to exert significant effort on behalf of the organization; and a definite desire to maintain organizational membership [11]. In this study, the concept of OC pertains to the extent to which members of the police academy and state police school in Indonesia identify with the organization, managerial objectives, and exhibit a willingness to invest effort, participate in decision-making, and internalize management values.

In this regard, Huynh and Hua [1] highlighted that several police officials possess a low level of commitment to the organization, partly due to the perceived misalignment in PsyCap and CA within the organization. This statement provides a broader perspective on OC in jobs and influencing constructs, such as PsyCap [12], [13]. Further, it is noted that the significant role of PsyCap within organization members can contribute to securing commitment levels and organizational sustainability [13]. Drawing on the conservation of resources (COR) theory from Chen *et al.* [2] the primary motivation of organizational members is to accumulate, protect, and deploy resources to safeguard and support oneself.

Elevated PsyCap levels in organization members positively impact health, well-being, and performance outcomes [14]. Tang *et al.* [15] remarked in their study that PsyCap reflects the positive mental energy of the police workforce and is an intangible yet vital asset for organizations. In this context, previous research [16] proposed the concept of PsyCap as the core construct of an individual's positive psychological state referring to self-efficacy, hope, optimism, and resilience, aligning with assertions by Sukoco and Lee [17]. For individuals, PsyCap can positively assist organization members in adapting to environments and perceived work stress; cultivating competitive excellence; and enhancing their well-being [18].

Gong *et al.* [19] conceptualize CA in the police workforce as the extent to which organization members are prepared for predictable career tasks, role involvement, and unforeseen challenges. Furthermore, Gao *et al.* [20] emphasized that CA epitomizes the ability of organization members to show initiative, fostering psychological safety through perceived work environments. Viewing CA similarly as a mediator, Kim and Kim [21] showed that employees with strong learning objectives tend to have higher commitment via CA. In other words, organization members with high learning objectives commit to the organization because they tend to invest more effort in learning and adapting to the organization and its roles [22]. Consequently, it can be inferred that organization members with high CA are more likely to commit to their respective organizations.

In the research of Gao *et al.* [20], it has been stated that PsyCap represents an important and very valuable personal resource that can facilitate the experience of organizational members during difficult times experienced, such as CA. In addition, the demonstrated aspects of PsyCap can help individuals address their ability to adapt to careers. This happens because PsyCap can increase employees' ability to adapt to new situations [22]. This fact encourages researchers to formulate a hypothesis: PsyCap contributes to CA (H1). In addition to PsyCap's ability to help individuals adapt, Gong *et al.* [19] stated that when individuals have confidence or optimism in facing challenges to develop in a challenging and uncertain environment, this will grow the commitment of individual members in their organization. Gong *et al.* [19] stated that one of the components of PsyCap, namely optimism, can help organizational members understand and have a positive view of work. Thus, they will have a positive attitude towards difficult times and be ready to engage with their organization [21]. This explanation leads to the following hypothesis: PsyCap contributes to individual OC in the organization (H2).

Career adaptability has been mentioned as the extent to which organizational members are prepared to face predictable careers, role involvement, and unexpected challenges [19]. Existing research findings prove that CA is overall significant to organizational members' sense of suitability with the job and organization [23]. It is further said that the balance between employees and values, career goals for the future leads to a stronger sense of well-being. When individuals feel satisfied with their career characteristics and job opportunities, this is proven to significantly influence OC at work [23]. Kim and Kim [21] proved in their research that towards OC perceived by organizational members, the resilience factor can help them to overcome the difficulties they face in their ability to pursue a career. It was further explained that the resilience factor is another aspect of PsyCap which is proven to be positively related to OC through the ability to adapt to a career. This encourages researchers to develop a hypothesis: CA has a positive relationship with OC (H3) and PsyCap through CA contributes to OC (H4).

Previous research indicates that PsyCap can enhance organizational performance and member behaviors, but fails to clearly explore the underlying mechanism of individual PsyCap's influence on organizations. Additionally, past studies identified by the researcher utilize PsyCap as a variable denoting OC without other constructs as mediators [23]. Therefore, it can be deduced that studies identifying OC with mediating constructs, such as CA, remain underexplored, especially in the police workforce. The researcher aims to elucidate the underlying mechanisms of OC by employing PsyCap as an antecedent and CA as the mediator of the relationship. To bolster the theoretical argument, this study adopts the COR theory to provide a clearer depiction of how PsyCap and CA assist organization members in enhancing OC when evaluating the quality of the police workforce in workplaces. The following is the conceptual framework of this research shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Research model scheme

2. RESEARCH METHOD

2.1. Research subjects and sampling techniques

This study is an explanatory survey research with a quantitative approach. Research employing a quantitative approach tests theories and proposed hypotheses using numbers and statistics in the data analysis process [24]. This research was conducted at the police academy and the state police school in Indonesia. The sampling technique used was non-probability sampling, and samples were taken using purposive sampling with the criteria specifically targeting novice police officers who recently graduated from the Police Academy and the State Police School in Indonesia. The population of this study was alumni of those academy, academic year 2022/2023. The calculation with Slovin formulation with total population is 4,530 and margin of error is 5%. Based on that calculation, we got 368 sample. We also attach 10% of sample size. Adding 10% to the sample size in research accounts for potential non-responses or data loss, ensuring the statistical reliability of the study results [17]. This buffer also compensates for any unexpected variability or incomplete data within the collected samples. Based on the calculation, the total sample consisted of 417 individuals representing police academy and state police school in Indonesia. The gender of respondents was 3% female and 97% male. The study utilized three variables, namely PsyCap as the independent variable, CA as the mediator, and OC as the dependent variable.

2.2. Research instruments

For the independent variable, namely PsyCap, the research instrument was adopted from previous studies [17], [25]. It encompasses four dimensions: hope (comprising 6 items), efficacy (comprising 6 items), resilience (comprising 6 items), and optimism (comprising 6 items). For the mediation variable, CA, the research instrument was derived from study Maggiori *et al.* [26] and comprises dimensions of concern, control, curiosity, and confidence, each with six statement items. The OC instrument, serving as the dependent variable, was adopted from Nguyen and Ngo [27], consisting of affective, normative, and continuance dimensions with a total of 8 items. Data collection employed a questionnaire technique. The measurement scale used in composing this instrument was a five-point Likert scale with ratings from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). Following the data collection phase, data were screened, processed, and analyzed using the statistical software package, SmartPLS. This software was chosen as the research framework proposed in this study encompasses several constructs to model relationships [28]. The instrument's reliability was gauged by examining the internal consistency of the sample, which is statistically determined using the procedure developed by Cronbach. Then, to measure the validity of a questionnaire, researcher use discriminant and convergent validity. The validity and reliability of the instrument will be discussed in more detail in the results section of the outer model.

2.3. Data analysis techniques

SmartPLS was used for regression analysis and hypothesis testing. The R^2 value is instrumental in measuring the level of variance from exogenous variables to endogenous variables. The subsequent procedure involves testing the proposed hypothesis by examining the path coefficient. The t-statistic value indicates the significance of the prediction model in partial least squares (PLS) if the $t\text{-statistic} > t\text{-table}$ (significant). Hypothesis testing is conducted bivariate by comparing the t-table with the t-statistic. In hypothesis testing, the beta coefficient value in SmartPLS employs the original sample, which is the unstandardized beta score, used to ascertain the predictive nature of exogenous variables on endogenous variables [29]. A positive beta coefficient indicates a positive influence, whereas a negative value indicates a negative impact of the exogenous variable on the endogenous variable with 95% significance. Specifically, for testing mediation effects, the Sobel test technique is used [30]. Its primary aim is to discern the influence of the mediation variable (CA). A variable is considered a mediating or intervening variable if it affects the relationship between the independent and dependent variables. The Sobel test technique involves testing the strength of the indirect influence of PsyCap (X) on OC (Y) through the CA (M) variable. The indirect effect (X to Y via M) is calculated by multiplying the XM path (a) with the MY path (b) or ab [31].

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Results

3.1.1. Outer model test results

The measurement model was evaluated based on three primary criteria: consistency reliability, convergent validity, and discriminant validity. The composite reliability (CR) score for each construct should be above 0.70 to ensure the internal consistency of the measurement. The convergent validity of a construct is assessed from the values of outer loadings and the average variance extracted (AVE). Each item's outer loading should be above 0.70, while the AVE should exceed 0.50 [32]. Although some outer loading values are lower than 0.70, they can still be deemed acceptable since their AVE values are greater than 0.50. Therefore, convergent validity was established for all variables in this study. The AVE of each construct must be greater than its highest squared correlation with any other construct [33]. The cross-loading value of each item for its construct should be higher than its cross-loading on other constructs. Figure 2 demonstrates that the cross-loading value of each item for its construct is the highest compared to other construct values in the same row and column. Thus, this indicates that discriminant validity was established as the findings met the requirements for discriminant validity.

3.1.2. Validity and reliability test results

Creswell stated that research results are considered valid if there is a congruence between the collected data and the actual data occurring in the studied object [34]. According to Neuman [35], an instrument is said to be reliable if it consistently produces the same results every time a measurement is performed. The questionnaire's validity was tested using discriminant and convergent validity to ensure that the questionnaire has valid items [36]. Moreover, to ensure that the respondents, consisting of the police academy and national police school alumni, understood the questionnaire without ambiguity, the research instrument's validity was thus established. The reliability of the instrument was assessed to check how consistently items measure in the same way when used under the same conditions with the same sample [37].

The instrument's reliability was maximized by employing clear factor conceptualization and ensuring accurate measurement, in addition to operationalizing each factor group with multiple indicators [38]. Subsequently, the questionnaire was pre-tested and modified to ensure comprehensibility. The instrument's reliability was gauged by examining the internal consistency of the sample, which is statistically determined using the procedure developed by Cronbach in 1951 [29]. Cronbach's alpha divides all questions in the instrument feasibly and computes the correlation value for items. The research model's convergent validity test was conducted through the calculation of outer loading values. An indicator is considered valid if it has a correlation (outer loading) value above 0.50 [39]. The results of the outer loading can be seen in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Validity testing based on factor loading

Based on the factor loading validity test as illustrated in Figure 2, the values for the variable PsyCap are as: i) for the dimension of hope, the values are 0.760, 0.785, 0.724, 0.778, 0.838, and 0.738; ii) for the efficacy dimension, they are 0.824, 0.756, 0.767, 0.795, 0.782, and 0.730; iii) for resilience, the values are 0.781, 0.786, 0.731, 0.807, 0.774, and 0.690; and iv) for optimism, they stand at 0.785, 0.791, 0.661, 0.783, 0.749, and 0.720. For the CA variable, under the concern dimension, the values are 0.774, 0.742, 0.745, 0.723, 0.742, and 0.748; for control, they are 0.701, 0.772, 0.712, 0.777, 0.725, and 0.796; for curiosity, the values are 0.758, 0.699, 0.740, 0.768, 0.808, and 0.701; and for confidence, they are 0.784, 0.717, 0.781, 0.711, 0.717, and 0.747. As for the OC variable, the values for the affective dimension are 0.848, 0.653, 0.750, 0.824, 0.836, 0.654, 0.773, and 0.856; for normative, they are 0.698, 0.811, 0.799, 0.731, 0.718, 0.794, 0.742, and 0.632; and for continuance, the values are 0.737, 0.732, 0.725, 0.712, 0.747, 0.708, 0.778, and 0.707. It is observed that the outer loading values vary, with some being greater than 0.7 and others less. Researchers often encounter weaker outer loadings. However, it is also advised that researchers should not discard indicators with outer loading values as long as the AVE exceeds 0.50, and there is not an excessive inclination to enhance CR [40]. Meanwhile, the evaluation of construct validity is discerned from the AVE value, which must exceed the stipulated 0.50. The results from each indicator's outer loading and the AVE of each variable composing the structural research model are displayed in Table 1.

Subsequently, validity testing was conducted based on the AVE value. The final evaluation of the outer model involved reliability testing. This reliability test aimed to observe the consistency of measurements for variables used in the structural model. Reliability testing in PLS was carried out in two ways: by evaluating the CR value and Cronbach's alpha for each variable. A variable is considered to have met CR if both its CR and Cronbach's alpha values exceed 0.70. The data that have been presented in Table 1 are CR and Cronbach alpha values for each research variable used in the model. The recommended AVE value is above 0.50 [41]. It is observed that all AVE values are >0.5, indicating that they have met the validity criteria based on AVE. Reliability testing was then conducted based on the CR value [42]. The suggested CR value is above 0.7 [43]. Notably, all CR values are >0.7, signifying that they have fulfilled the reliability criteria based on CR. Reliability testing then proceeded based on the value of Cronbach's alpha (CA). The recommended Cronbach's alpha value is above 0.70 [29]. All Cronbach's alpha values are observed to be >0.7. The Cronbach's alpha values for all constructs range from 0.838 to 0.961, all of which are substantially above the suggested reliability standard of 0.70 [29], [35], [42]. Hence, the internal consistency of the instrument is demonstrated. All these metrics indicate that the instrument is valid for further analysis. In the discriminant validity testing, assessment was made based on the Fornell-Larcker criterion, as shown in Table 2.

The square root of the AVE for a latent variable was compared to the correlation value between that latent variable and other latent variables. It was observed that the square root of the AVE for each latent variable, namely PsyCap-PsyCap, is larger than the correlation values of PsyCap-CA and PsyCap-OC. Additionally, the square root of the AVE for each latent variable, namely CA-CA and OC-OC, is larger than the correlation value between CA and OC. Thus, it can be concluded that the criteria for discriminant validity have been met.

Table 1. Results of convergent validity and reliability testing

Variable-dimension	Cronbach alpha	CR	AVE	Convergent validity
PsyCap	0.961	0.964	0.526	Yes
Hope	0.863	0.898	0.595	
Efficacy	0.868	0.901	0.603	
Resilience	0.855	0.893	0.581	
Optimism	0.843	0.885	0.562	
CA	0.957	0.960	0.503	Yes
Concern	0.840	0.883	0.556	
Control	0.842	0.884	0.559	
Curiosity	0.841	0.883	0.558	
Confidence	0.838	0.881	0.553	
OC	0.957	0.960	0.505	Yes
Affective	0.905	0.924	0.605	
Normative	0.883	0.907	0.552	
Continuance	0.876	0.902	0.535	

Table 2. Fornell-Larcker

Variable	PsyCap	CA	OC
PsyCap	0.725		
CA	0.350	0.709	
OC	0.249	0.620	0.710

3.1.3. Inner model test results

The structural model is evaluated through path coefficients and R^2 values. Previous research has established acceptable ranges for R^2 values to be 0.75 (substantial), 0.50 (moderate), and 0.25 (weak) [33]. Table 3 displays the bootstrapping results of the entire model and path coefficient assessment.

3.1.4. Path coefficient test results

Path coefficients are instrumental in indicating the directionality of relationships between variables, specifically whether a hypothesis reflects a positive or negative direction. Path coefficients range from -1 to 1. Values within the range of 0 to 1 are considered positive, while those ranging from -1 to 0 are negative. The path coefficients of each exogenous (independent) variable concerning the endogenous (dependent) variable in the study are illustrated in Table 1 [37]. The outer model evaluation in partial least square analysis is elucidated based on the algorithm estimation results of the research model using SmartPLS Version 3.2.9, which are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Path coefficient and significance test

Relationship	Original sample (o)	Sample mean (m)	Standard deviation (stdev)	T-Stat.	P values
PsyCap>CA	0.350	0.351	0.048	7.277	0.000*
PsyCap>OC	0.036	0.034	0.043	0.849	0.396
CA>OC	0.607	0.607	0.032	18.903	0.000*
PsyCap>CA>OC	0.213	0.213	0.032	6.701	0.000*

*=significant at 0.05 level of significance

From Table 3, it is evident that the relationship between PsyCap and CA has a positive coefficient of 0.350, with a p-value of 0.000* and a t-value of 7.277 ($t > 1.96$), denoting a statistically significant positive association. This suggests that as PsyCap increases, CA is inclined to increase as well. The direct relationship between PsyCap and OC, indicated by a coefficient of 0.036, has a p-value of 0.396 and a t-value of 0.849 ($t < 1.96$), which is statistically not significant (since the p-value exceeds the generally accepted threshold of 0.05). This implies that without accounting for CA as a mediator, there's no clear evidence suggesting a significant direct impact of PsyCap on OC in this study.

The relationship between CA and OC shows a substantial coefficient of 0.607, with a p-value of 0.000* and a t-value of 18.903 ($t > 1.96$), signifying a very significant positive association. This indicates that CA has a profound influence on OC, suggesting that as CA rises, so does OC. Considering the indirect relationship (through mediation) between PsyCap and OC and factoring in the mediating effect of CA, the result yields a coefficient of 0.213, with a p-value of 0.000* and a t-value of 6.701 ($t > 1.96$). This indicates a significant positive influence of PsyCap on OC mediated through CA.

Based on these results, it is inferred that CA fully mediates the relationship between PsyCap and OC. The "full mediation" concept implies that the mediator (in this case, CA) entirely accounts for the relationship between the independent variable (PsyCap) and the dependent variable (OC) [30]. This means that, after accounting for the mediator, there is no direct link between the independent and dependent variables, rendering the direct relationship between PsyCap and OC non-significant.

3.1.5. R-square test results

R-squared is a figure ranging between 0 and 1 that reflects the combined influence of independent variables on the dependent variable's value. The R-squared (R^2) value is utilized to determine the extent to which a specific independent latent variable impacts a dependent latent variable [33]. The R-square value for CA is found to be 0.123, implying that PsyCap influences CA by 12.3%, and for OC, it's 0.385, indicating that both PsyCap and CA jointly influence OC by 38.50%.

3.2. Discussion

Various aspects of PsyCap have been demonstrated to have a strong association with OC [43]. A study by Tyagi [44] found a positive correlation between PsyCap and OC. This positive correlation is believed to arise because employees with higher levels of self-efficacy, hope, optimism, and resilience are more likely to possess elevated cognitive and behavioral confidence, greater resilience to adverse situations, and optimism when facing challenging situations. Thus, they are more likely to be committed to their organizations. However, in this study, PsyCap showed a non-significant positive relationship with OC. This is attributed to the fact that alumni of the police academy and the national police school in Indonesia already possess a high PsyCap, a prerequisite for passing their police academy's selection process. Hence, upon graduation, they are duty-bound to serve the public in their early days as police officers. Therefore, they might increase OC if they possess good CA skills.

In previous studies [45], [46], it was found that PsyCap positively influences OC. Rego *et al.* [47] stated that there exists a positive correlation between the optimism dimension of PsyCap and OC. In a study by Xu *et al.* [48], PsyCap contributes only about 6% to OC. In another research, it was mentioned that PsyCap is a significant predictor of OC [49]. Thus, it can be inferred that the level of PsyCap of lecturers is an essential factor in explaining and enhancing OC among police academy alumni, albeit not significant.

Enhancing the PsyCap of alumni from the police academy and national police school in Indonesia can aid them in managing or negotiating their fit with workgroups, jobs, or organizations as a career aspect. PsyCap can influence CA outcomes, which subsequently impacts OC to retain valuable and talented staff. Employees who feel highly committed are likely to perceive their relationship with their superiors as long-term and have a lower intent to quit compared to those with lesser levels of attachment and commitment to their organization [50].

Findings indicate that the behavioral adaptability, self-management, and interpersonal skills of alumni from the police academy and national police school in Indonesia, along with clarity about their future career direction, are crucial in enhancing their OC. Additionally, their overall CA is significantly associated with their PsyCap. Greater congruence between an employee's values, career objectives, future plans, and

company culture, as well as direct job demands (e.g., job knowledge, skills, and abilities), leads to a stronger sense of belonging [51]. Duffy *et al.* [52] showed that employees' satisfaction with their career opportunities and job characteristics (autonomy, skill variety, and challenge) significantly correlates with their OC.

To elaborate further, it is imperative that interventions for career development within organizations concentrate on enhancing the meta-capacities related to psychological career aspects, as highlighted in this research, being crucial psychosocial assets for enhancing the OC of the National Police School and Police Academy alumni. Developing employees' CA resources encourages proactive career behaviors, which will assist them in formulating problem-solving strategies and coping behaviors necessary for integrating their self-concept with their role as police officers. This harmoniously negotiates the person-environment fit, thus boosting OC [53].

The author introduces the concept of CA, defining it as a composite of five distinct attitudes, beliefs, and competencies—namely attention, control, curiosity, confidence, and commitment. These elements collectively constitute practical problem-solving strategies and coping mechanisms employed by individuals to harmonize their vocational self-concept with their professional roles [54]. PsyCap serves as a personal resource in managing a harmonious person-environment alignment. For instance, PsyCap (hope, efficacy, resilience, and optimism) enables individuals to adapt to changes in CA and to shape and select environments for success in specific socio-cultural contexts [55].

Hardiness, perceived as a type of PsyCap and a career resource, is characterized as an amalgamation of personality attributes associated with commitment, control, and challenge. Individuals possessing a high degree of hardiness are inclined to engage with full commitment in their endeavors, maintain a belief in and actively attempt to exert influence over the events of their lives, and perceive change not merely as a typical occurrence, but also as an opportunity or challenge that fosters personal growth and development [56], [57]. Moreover, other research has proven that PsyCap is perceived to have proactive coping mechanisms that can assist the alumni of the police academy and national police school in Indonesia in effectively managing stress [58]. When someone has high PsyCap, it becomes easier for them to expect positive occurrences at the workplace and trust their capabilities to create future success. This, in turn, enhances the individual's OC [59].

4. CONCLUSION

This research discusses the relationship between PsyCap and OC with the mediating role of CA using an explanatory survey system within the context of alumni from the Police Academy and the State Police School in Indonesia. The initial step utilized in this conceptual model entailed the dissemination of questionnaires, followed by filtering, processing, and data analysis using the statistical software package, SmartPLS. The model was further validated through various constructs to depict the relationships. Findings indicate that all research hypotheses were accepted, and the exogenous variable model could explain between 12.3% to 38.5% of the endogenous variables.

However, this study also presents several limitations. Firstly, the research focuses solely on the role of PsyCap in predicting OC levels. Subsequent research might consider an analysis incorporating additional variables to elucidate OC. In this context, the researcher suggests incorporating leadership constructs, specifically transformational leadership. Secondly, this research is limited to confirming theory generalization. Thus, future studies should consider extensive data collection for population generalization. Thirdly, this study only analyzes the mediating role in supporting the direct relationship to the OC variable. Further research might incorporate moderating constructs to achieve more comprehensive research findings. For this, the researcher suggests the use of perceived social support.

This research has theoretical and practical contribution. Theoretically, this enriches the understanding of PsyCap by identifying its nuanced relationship with OC in high PsyCap environments, like police academies, and introduces CA as a potentially stronger predictor in such settings. Practically, this insight urges a recalibration of human resource strategies within police departments. Instead of solely concentrating on enhancing PsyCap, these strategies should also robustly incorporate CA development, thereby nurturing novice police officers' ability to effectively navigate occupational challenges and changes, which in turn solidifies their commitment to the force. This approach not only reinforces the officers' alignment with their roles and responsibilities but also potentially improves retention rates, especially among those in the early stages of their policing career.

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